

USING APPLIED IMPROVISATION TECHNIQUES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TO ENHANCE CREATIVE PROBLEM-SOLVING AND TEAMWORK SKILLS

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Abstract. *Today's technical problems have been magnified by both the volume of data collected and analyzed and the speed at which it is processed. Human beings cannot possibly understand all the implications of this data. Artificial intelligence (AI) does have the ability to shift through the data, but can it help a human makes sense of it all and can AI offer a viable solution. This presentation will cover aspects of AI as a teammate and how AI can and cannot help teams respond in pressure or crisis management situations where time is of the essence. This presentation is also designed for those who want to learn more about some of the various techniques used and how they can be incorporated into technical curriculums.*

Applied improvisation techniques can also be used in the teaching of technical concepts such as cybersecurity, agile development, database design, and programming concepts. It can also help to improve a student's communication and teamwork skills. This presentation is based on a course taught to the University of Cincinnati's School of Information Technology graduate students on creative problem-solving (CPS). It incorporated the Basadur CPS methodology along with a focus on how to build a team story, changing one's thinking, acceptance of self-failings, and ideas on how to better communicate diverse ideas. The use of AI was also introduced.

This presentation is designed to raise awareness of AI as a teammate and questions that need to be explored if AI-human teams are to be successful in general and in crisis situations in particular. This work is ongoing and further research and development needs to be done.

Ccs concepts. *Social and professional topics*

Keywords: *Improvisation, soft skills, creative problem-solving*

1 Critical Soft Skills

According to the World Economic Forum's (WEF) Future of Jobs Report 2020 [2] the top 15 skills for 2025 are: 1. Analytical thinking and innovation, 2. Active learning and learning strategies, 3. Complex problem-solving, 4. Critical thinking and analysis, 5. Creativity, originality, and initiative, 6. Leadership and social influence, 7. Technology use, monitoring and control, 8. Technology design and programming, 9. Resilience, stress tolerance, and flexibility, 10. Reasoning, problem-solving, and ideation, 11. Emotional intelligence, 12. Troubleshooting and user experience, 13. Service orientation, 14. Systems analysis and evaluation, 15. Persuasion and negotiation.

Another report, the Skills Framework for the Information Age (SFIA) [3] [4] has 12 themes with one of them being "People and skills" which is broken down into 11 categories: 1. Communication skills, 2. Planning, 3. Problem solving, 4. Influence, 5. Collaboration, 6. Delegation, 7. Creativity, 8. Leadership, 9. Execution performance, 10. Decision making, 11. Leadership and professional development.

There are seven establish computing curricula that are recognized by ABET and summarized in the Computing Curricula 2020 Paradigms for Global Computing Education (CC2020) [5]. They are: Computer Engineering (CE2016) [6], Computer Science (CS2023) [7],

Cybersecurity (CSec2017) [8], Data Science (DS2021) [9], Information Systems (IS2020) [10], Information Technology (IT2017) [1], and Software Engineering (SE2014) [11]. The CC2020 report covers the technical distinctions and overlap amongst each of these disciplines along with a curriculum framework. Only the CE2016 and IT2017 reports use the words "soft skills" more than 2 times. IT2017 report used the term 25 times overall and CE2016 used the term 13 times. The DS2021, IS2020, and SE2014 reports do not use the term at all, but do incorporate the key ideas of what "soft skills" means.

2 Applied Improvisation

There is a fair amount of relevant research, articles, and talks on the use of improvisation outside of artistic improvisation. For example, the Applied Improv Network (AIN) although officially founded in 2002 traces its roots to the mid-1990s when people began to see the value in applying and using improvisation techniques to organizations with situations that required a reactive response. This is the same time in which academics began researching into what today is called organizational improvisation (OI). AIN was created to help professionals who believe that the lessons learned in artistic improvisation could be applied to the professional world. Organizational improvisation (OI) research similarly goes back to the mid-1990s and is rooted in work done by Karl Weick and others.

3 Artificial Intelligence as a Teammate

Human-AI teams are being studied. The results of some of the research suggest that while AI can help a team perform better a certain level of trust is needed. AI as a teammate requires humans to better understand the AI system and vice-versa. Humans and animals, especially dogs, have created a bond and an understanding that goes back centuries. Of course, both humans and dogs cease to exist (we die), but not the AI. Teams change members constantly so there is the challenge of getting a new teammate up to speed. Research indicates that a human-in-the loop (HITL) is important so that no AI can completely make a decision without some additional human thought or input. Also, AI systems need to learn how to forget old methods and how to brainstorm new ones as situations evolve.

3.1 Mann Gulch Forest Fire Lesson

The Mann Gulch forest fire occurred in 1949 in the Helena National Forest in Montana, United States. Thirteen out of 16 persons involved died because of the fire making a sudden shift in its direction. One of 3 survivors make an on-the-spot decision that saved his life while the other two were able to get in-between a rock protected crevice.

It is not that this fire is any more important than any other forest fires or other life-or-death situations. It is that this fire was the subject of extensive analysis done by Karl Weick in 1993 that gave rise to organizational improvisation research. One of the issues that came out of this research was that the introduction of a new member to a team especially a new manager or leader can cause resistance from the "followers". In the Mann Gulch Forest fire, the new team lead, Wagner Dodge, improvised a never tried before method that saved himself, but he was unable to get the others to follow because of the lack of trust and time for the team members to make an informed decision.

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This presentation is based upon a semester course that was given back in the Spring-2022 semester to our graduate students and various workshops conducted on creative problem-solving and applied improvisation over the past several years. This course also incorporated the UN 17 Sustainable Development Goals in order to give students a real life set of problems that can involve an IT solution.

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